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CARPOS

Coachable Robot for Fruit
Picking Operations

D1- Requirements, use-cases and KPIs of CARPOS

Abstract:

The purpose of the present deliverable is to report on the user needs and expectations from the CARPOS robotic system and describe the user requirements, as well as the CARPOS project use cases that derived from the conducted analysis. In this scope, the present deliverable reports the results of the user requirement collection and analysis performed. More specifically, the requirements, related measures and respective Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for autonomous robotic fruit picking operations are investigated and defined, based on the Objectives set to the description of action (Technical Document). Both the requirements and the related measures are in turn drafted to both the technical experts and the agriculture-related scientists of the project for evaluating their importance. Based on this evaluation, the KPIs of the project are finally defined. Furthermore, from among the fruit picking operations, the process of drafting the use-cases is conducted, that capture and put to challenge the system requirements for the proposed technologies. The system requirements defined, as well as their importance will be utilized for constructing the overall architecture of the solution and alongside with the use-cases and the KPIs will constitute the pillars for the experimental evaluation and testing conducted in WP6 of the project

Dissemination Level: **PU**

Περίληψη στα Ελληνικά:

Σκοπός του παρόντος παραδοτέου είναι η αναφορά των αναγκών και των προσδοκιών των χρηστών από το ρομποτικό σύστημα CARPOS και η περιγραφή των απαιτήσεων των χρηστών, καθώς και των σεναρίων χρήσης του έργου CARPOS που προέκυψαν από την ανάλυση που διενεργήθηκε. Προς αυτή την κατεύθυνση, το παρόν παραδοτέο αναφέρει τα αποτελέσματα της συλλογής και ανάλυσης των απαιτήσεων χρήστη που πραγματοποιήθηκαν. Πιο συγκεκριμένα, διερευνώνται και καθορίζονται οι απαιτήσεις, οι σχετικές μετρικές (Related measures - RMs) και οι αντίστοιχοι Βασικοί Δείκτες Επίδοσης (Key Performance Indicators - KPIs) για αυτόνομες ρομποτικές εργασίες συλλογής φρούτων, με βάση τους στόχους που έχουν τεθεί στην περιγραφή της δράσης (Τεχνικό Έγγραφο). Τόσο οι απαιτήσεις όσο και οι σχετικές μετρικές συντάσσονται με τη σειρά τους τόσο στους τεχνικούς εμπειρογνώμονες όσο και στους συνεργαζόμενους γεωπόνους του έργου για την αξιολόγηση της σημασίας τους. Βάσει της βαθμολόγησης των παραπάνω, εξάγονται τελικά οι δείκτες αξιολόγησης του έργου. Επιπλέον, μεταξύ των εργασιών συλλογής φρούτων, διεξάγεται η διαδικασία σύνταξης των σεναρίων χρήσης, που βασίζονται στις απαιτήσεις συστήματος για τις προτεινόμενες τεχνολογίες. Οι απαιτήσεις συστήματος, όπως αυτές καθορίζονται στο παρόν έγγραφο, καθώς και η σημασία τους θα χρησιμοποιηθούν για την κατασκευή της συνολικής αρχιτεκτονικής της λύσης και παράλληλα με τα σενάρια χρήσης και τους δείκτες επίδοσης θα αποτελέσουν τους πυλώνες για την πειραματική αξιολόγηση και δοκιμή που θα πραγματοποιηθεί στο Πακέτο Εργασίας 6 (WP6) του έργου.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Current harvesting techniques performed by humans, is mainly performed either using a cutting tool/device, such as the harvesting of grapes, or without cutting tools, i.e. by hand, such as apple or peach picking. In order to distinguish between the two categories, we will henceforth refer to the latter one as “fruit picking” operation. Harvesting through fruit picking ensures the safety of the plant, the fruit, the farmer and/or the surrounding human workers, while in some cases it is easier to perform than harvesting using a cutting tool/device. In particular, there are many cases in which the fruit is very close or even attached to the surrounding environment, e.g. branches, leaves etc., without leaving cutting affordances (avoiding in this way the transmission of phytopathological diseases between healthy and diseased plants). Furthermore, when picking the fruit without a cutting tool the safety of the farmer and the surrounding human workers is ensured, as there are no dangerous tools involved in the process. Some examples of such fruit picking operations are detailed in Chapter 2 of this deliverable.

To automate fruit picking using a robotic system, currently available solutions propose the explicit programming of the robot involving the specification of exact motion and/or force patterns in order to detach the fruit from the plant. This process requires considerable technical knowledge, it is time-consuming and lacks flexibility and adaptability to different types of crops. Moreover, in such cases, the life-long experience of farmers is not fully exploited to improve the effectiveness and performance of the robotic fruit picking action.

The CARPOS project aims at providing a novel, coachable and human-friendly mobile robotic system, equipped with a robotic manipulator and multiple sensors, able of capturing and exploiting the lifelong experience of farmers through Learning by Demonstration (LbD), in order to successfully perform autonomous fruit picking operations. To achieve this, the system will be capable of intuitively accumulating knowledge through both kinesthetic and/or visual coaching by the human farmers, during its operation, thereby providing easy deployment, as well as flexibility and adaptability to different types of crops. Through the use of an intuitive human-machine interface, the farmer will be able to monitor the process performed by the robot, and correct it whenever deemed necessary, by using the above coaching means.

The goal of this deliverable is to conduct a review of users' needs and expectations in order to determine the CARPOS robot ecosystem's requirements and define the project's target use cases. More specifically, in Chapter 2, some representative fruit picking operations currently performed by human farmers are briefly presented. From those scenarios, two are selected as the use cases of the CARPOS project, namely that of the tomato (Elpida variety) and the prickly pear picking. The selected use cases are presented in detail in Chapter 3. In Chapter 4, the system requirements, related measures (RMs) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are detailed. The system requirements and KPIs are built based on the Objectives of the project, via the RMs, and reflect the system targeted functionalities, e.g. the fruit picking performance, the safety of the fruit, the plant etc.

1.1 RELATION TO OTHER DELIVERABLES

The present deliverable will provide the basis for defining the final CARPOS system architecture and technical specifications. Both the use cases and the KPIs will serve as the guidelines for the final testing of the system, i.e. D8 - System Integration and testing, but also will give the scientific directions and aims for all the technical deliverables, i.e.: D3 - Fruit picking action identification and skill extraction from visual observation, D4 - Control schemes for occlusion-free active perception, D5 - Controller for unintentional and intentional pHRI during the coaching and autonomous operation, D6 - Graphical human-machine interface and skill extraction through proprioceptive data, D7 - Multimodal skill encoding and generalization in fruit geometry variations. The KPIs will play the role of our main metrics for evaluating the system during the development of the different modules, while the use cases will serve as the main testing setups for testing and developing the modules.

2. FRUIT PICKING OPERATIONS PERFORMED BY HUMAN

Understanding the way humans grasp and detach the tomato fruits, including the factors and limitations that affect each type of grasp, as well as the typical grasp used in tomato picking, holds great scientific importance for ergonomic design and the development of efficient harvesting robot finger strategies. Human grasps can be categorized as power grasp and precision grasp (Napier, 1956¹). The power grasp is used to grasp larger size fruits such as apples, pears and peach while precision grasp (three-finger pinch) is usually employed in small size fruits such as berries, prickly pears, and cherries. Concomitantly, after each individual fruit has been detached from the branch, the farmer places them in specially designed storage crates minimizing post-harvest losses. Additionally, fruit sorting and packaging takes place either immediately after harvest in the field (i.e. strawberries) or after they have been transferred in the packing house (i.e. tomatoes), depending on a specific physiological characteristic of each plant species which determines the ripening process of the fruit before and after they have been harvested from the plants. Climacteric fruits have a fast period of ripening during which they change color and develop flavor and aroma and will continue ripen after they are harvested (i.e. bananas, tomatoes, pears, mangos, peaches, apples, and avocados) while non-climacteric plants produce fruits which stop ripen after the product has been harvested.

Types of human-like tomato grasps

As per Feix et al. (2016)², the grasp taxonomy defines four distinct grasp types: Power palm-Thumb abduction, Power palm-Thumb adduction, Power pad-Thumb abduction and Pinch. In the Power palm-Thumb abduction type, the fingers, palm, and thumb wrap simultaneously around the tomato fruit, with the thumb generally opposed to the other fingers. In the Power palm-Thumb

¹ NAPIER JR. The prehensile movements of the human hand. *J Bone Joint Surg Br.* 1956 Nov;38-B(4):902-13. doi: 10.1302/0301-620X.38B4.902. PMID: 13376678.

² T. Feix, J. Romero, H. -B. Schmiebmayer, A. M. Dollar and D. Kragic, "The GRASP Taxonomy of Human Grasp Types," in *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 66-77, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1109/THMS.2015.2470657.

adduction type, the fingers and palm wrap around the tomato fruit, while the thumb is adducted on the side of the fingers. In the Power pad-Thumb abduction type, the fingers and thumb wrap around the tomato fruit, with at least two contact regions with each finger; the thumb opposes the other fingers, and the tomato fruit does not directly come into contact with the palm. In the Pinch type, the fingers and thumb squeeze the opposite sides of the tomato using fingertips without coming into contact with the palm.

Figure 1. Four grasping types according to Feix et al. (2016), i) power palm-thumb abduction type, ii) power palm-thumb adduction type, iii) power pad-thumb abduction type and iv) pinch type (from left to right).

3. THE USE CASES OF CARPOS

Fruit picking is currently mainly performed manually, e.g. by farmers. It imposes high physical and cognitive load to the worker, as it often involves non-ergonomic postures (kneeling or lifting the elbow above the level of shoulder) over long working hours and thus it is considered to risk the farmer's health, in both short and life-long terms.

To demonstrate and test the targeted functionalities, the objectives fulfillment, the effectiveness and the impact of the proposed solutions, we employ two scenarios of fruit picking, involving different fruit geometries, motion patterns, requirements and restrictions. The use cases are designed to reveal the potential added value gained from our developed methodologies and the generalization of our solutions to different crop types. Notably, these particular use cases cover a representative set in which the developed solutions will be applied, as they involve different motion patterns and different non-ergonomic positions, when performed by a human, namely that of kneeling (possibly the case in tomato picking) and that of lifting the elbow above the shoulder level (possibly the case in prickly pears picking). The selected use cases will sufficiently demonstrate the impact of the CARPOS solutions to this challenging task, once undertaken by our envisioned AI-powered robot.

All scenarios assume an initial posture for the plant, i.e. that the robot is already in proximity of the plant. The scenarios involve the teaching of the activity by the human, as stated in the task description of the project. More specifically, in both use cases the following functionalities will be tested:

- The ability of the robot to observe the human motion and request (if needed) iterations for gathering more information
- The ability of the robot to kinesthetically correct the motion, when interrupted by the human when performing the task.

- The ability of the robot to reproduce the motion captured by both visual and kinesthetic means.
- The human-machine interface
- The ability of the system to generalize the task in various orientations and positions of the fruits.

For the initial experimentation and testing, mockup setups with plastic fruits will be utilized, such as the one depicted in Fig. 2a. However, for more realistic experimentation, a real- plant setup is under construction, depicted in Fig. 2b, which will be used extensively after its setup. In order to achieve continuous supply of tomato plants for the robotic experiments, 30 tomato seedling (var. ELPIDA) were transplanted in the greenhouse facilities of the Hellenic Mediterranean University. Tomato plants were cultivated in an open loop hydroponic system and at the stage of 2 fully mature tomato clusters, were transferred in a real-plant set up. The real-plant setup, in its final form, involves two fully developed tomato plants, along with the closed loop hydroponic system and a plant support system. The hydroponic system comprises of a single gutter, a nutrient solution tank (25 L), a pump (capacity of 3000 L/H) and a drip irrigation system with an individual emitter per plant at a flow rate of 4 L h⁻¹.

a) Mockup setup

b) real plant setup

Figure 2 – Experimental setups of the project

The two selected scenarios are listed below:

Scenario 1. Harvesting (fruit picking) of tomato (Elpida variety)

The tomato fruit-bearing system is defined as shown in Fig. 3 and involves several parts biologically distinguished between main stem and fruit like peduncle, pedicel, abscission zone, and calyx. The peduncle is a branch from the main stem, and it holds single or multiple pedicels where a branch holds an individual fruit. The pedicel can be divided anatomically into the distal and proximal pedicels based on the abscission zone, and the ripe fruit is detached physiologically by the abscission process in this zone. The abscission zone is important for harvesting as it comprises the fruit detachment point while retaining both the calyx and distal pedicel. **The farmer places their hand at the bottom part of the fruit with their thumb against the abscission zone, and moves the wrist against it, effectively using the fruit-calyx-distal pedicel apparatus as leverage for the zone to detach from the rest of the fruit cluster.**

Figure 3: Harvesting motion on Tomato (Elpida variety)

Scenario 2. Prickly pear picking

The harvest process of prickly pears, shown in Fig. 4, is considered one of the most difficult tasks during the cultivation process of this species due to the morphology and the presence of spikes both in shoots and fruits of the plant. It is preferable to harvest during the morning hours or in the afternoon, when the fruits appear some looseness and easily detach. Fruit harvesting is carefully performed by the farmer, using thick gloves or tools such as tweezers to avoid minor injuries during the process. The motion, regardless the use of a tool or not is always such the fruit rotates around the axis attached to the leaf, then when the fruit is loose it is either snapped with a downward motion of the wrist or if a knife is used, the remaining tissue is cut off. Additionally, fruit storage is delicately performed in spongy boxes to preserve the ideal postharvest characteristics of the fruit and increase shelf life of the product.

Figure 4: Prickly pear harvesting motion (yellow) and detachment point from the leaf (red). A plastic surface is used for the protection of the hand of the human.

4. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS AND KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The system requirements are defined based on the Objectives of the project which are the following (as taken from the description of action):

01: To develop novel Learning by Demonstration (LbD) methods that combine visual data (from the camera) and kinesthetic data (position and forces) for the incremental learning of fruit picking skills.

02: To develop new compliant control schemes that take into account the complete kinematic chain, i.e. the gripper, the robotic manipulator and the robotic platform will be considered as a single kinematic chain. The purpose of this compliant control scheme will be twofold: on the one hand it will enable the kinesthetic teaching of the picking skills (intentional pHRI) and on the other hand it will guarantee the safety of the surrounding humans (human-teacher, or workers in general) in case of possible unintentional collision.

03: To utilize and apply currently available computer vision solution to the problem of identifying: a) the fruit's geometry and pose, b) the configuration of the human hands and c) the contact points between the human fingers and the fruit.

04: To develop control schemes for the active perception (tracking) of the human hand, avoiding possible occlusions, in order to optimize the robot's observations of the human's motion pattern during the visual demonstration performed by the farmer.

05: To combine a mobile robotic platform, a robotic manipulator, a robotic gripper, an in-hand RGB-D camera (attached to the manipulator's end-effector), static RGB-D cameras (attached to the platform), force/torque sensors and 3D-printed robotic fingers, appropriately designed for fruit picking operations, as conceptually shown in Figure 3a, for the implementation and testing of the developed methodologies.

To test and evaluate the fulfilment of the defined System Requirements (SRs), several Related Measures (RM) were defined for each system requirement. The SRs and RMs related to Objective 5 are defined in order to evaluate the whole system performance and assess the impact of the proposed solution in real-life agricultural applications. After the definition of both SRs and RMs, their importance was quantified by the agricultural scientists of the project, based on the needs and specifications of both farmers and agricultural experts, as well as by the technical/research scientists of the project responsible for developing the different modules of the system. The SRs and RMs are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively, alongside with the quantified importance, provided by both the agricultural and the technology-development experts. In both Table 1 and 2, the correspondence between the SRs and RMs is also provided.

Table 1 – CARPOS System Requirements

Rel Obj	SR No	Description of the System Requirement	Related Metrics	SR Importance (experts)	
				Agric.	T.Dev.
O1	SR1.1	The robotic system should be able to learn the fruit picking skill from observing the human <u>once</u>	RMs 1.1-1.3	Very low	Low
	SR1.2	The robotic system should be able to learn the fruit picking skill from observing the human <u>executing the task multiple times, to learn it more precisely</u>	RMs 1.1-1.2, 1.4-1.5	Very high	High
	SR1.3	The robotic system should be able to <u>learn</u> the fruit picking skill from physical guidance by the human	RMs 1.6-1.8	Low	Moderate
	SR1.3	The robotic system should be able to <u>correct</u> the fruit picking skill learned, through physical guidance by the human	RMs 1.6-1.9	High	High
	SR1.4	The robotic system should be able to combine learning through visual observations and learning through physical guidance by the human	RMs 1.10	Low	High
	SR1.5	The system should include an easy and intuitive Human-machine interface	RMs 1.11, 1.12	High	High
O2	SR2.1	The robot should be safe for working close to humans	RMs 2.1 – 2.4	Very high	Very high
	SR2.2	The robot should be compliant when the human exerts forces to it	RMs 2.1 – 2.4, 2.6	Very high	Very high
	SR2.3	During the execution of the fruit picking task the robot should follow an exact motion pattern	RM 2.5	Moderate	Low
	SR2.4	The robot should be compliant, when physically guided by the human for motion corrections.	RMs 2.3 – 2.4, 2.6	High	High

	SR2.5	The robot should move both its robotic arm and its platform simultaneously when performing the task.	RM 2.7	Low	Moderate
03	SR3.1	The robotic system should be able to identify the fruit shape <u>for learning the skill</u> (<i>how much does the motion depend on the shape of the fruit for learning the task?</i>)	RM 3.1	High	Moderate
	SR3.2	The robotic system should be able to identify the fruit shape <u>for executing the fruit picking task</u> (<i>how much does the motion depend on the shape of the fruit for executing the task?</i>)	RM 3.1	High	High
	SR3.3	The robotic system should be able to identify the fruit orientation <u>for learning the skill</u>	RM 3.2	High	Moderate
	SR3.4	The robotic system should be able to identify the fruit orientation <u>for executing the fruit picking task</u>	RM 3.2	High	High
	SR3.5	The robotic system should be able to identify the exact fruit pose (position and orientation) <u>for learning the skill</u>	RMs 3.2, 3.3	Very high	Moderate
	SR3.6	The robotic system should be able to identify the exact fruit pose (position and orientation) <u>for executing the fruit picking task</u>	RMs 3.2, 3.3	Very high	High
	SR3.7	The robotic system should be able to identify the configuration of the human fingers <u>for learning the skill</u>	RM 3.4	Low	High
	SR3.8	The robotics system should be able to identify the contact points between the human fingers and the fruit <u>for learning the skill</u>	RM 3.5	Very high	High
04	SR4.1	The robotic system should be able to avoid any possible occlusion during the active observation of the human hand	RMs 4.1, 4.2	Moderate	High
	SR4.2	The robotic system should infer the motion of the human hand when this is occluded	RM 4.3	Moderate	Moderate
	SR4.3	The robotic system should be able to request for a new iteration if the observed motion was not visible for a long duration. In this case, the robotic system should be able to find a new point of view in order to “see” the previously hidden motion segments.	RM 4.4	Very high	High
05	SR5.1	The system should be able to learn the fruit picking skill from human demonstration	RM 5.1	High	High
	SR5.2	The system should be able to generalize the motion for any fruit of the same type	RM 5.2	High	High
	SR5.3	The system should be easily and intuitively adaptable to new fruit types	RM 5.3	Moderate	Moderate
	SR5.4	The system should imitate the human actions	RM 5.4	High	Moderate
	SR5.5	After the skill transfer by the human, the system should be able to harvest the fruits autonomously	RM 5.5, 5.6, 5.7	Very high	High

Table 2 – Related Measures (RMs)

KPI No	Description of the Key performance indicator	Value direction	SR Importance (experts)	
			Agric.	T.Dev.
RM 1.1	Smoothness of the captured human motion through vision	high	High	Moderate
RM 1.2	Number of iterations required for sufficiently capturing the human motion through vision	low	High	High
RM 1.3	Ability of the system to learn the skill using only one observation	high	Low	Moderate
RM 1.4	Cognitive load of human during the teaching through multiple visual observation	low	High	High
RM 1.5	Physical load of the human during the teaching through multiple visual observations	low	High	High
RM 1.6	Ability of the system to learn the skill using physical guidance	high	Moderate	-
RM 1.7	Cognitive load of human during the teaching through physical guidance	low	High	High
RM 1.8	Physical load of the human during the teaching through physical guidance	low	High	High
RM 1.9	Magnitude of corrections done after the physical intervention of the human for corrections	high	-	Moderate
RM 1.10	Magnitude of exploitation of data from both visual observation and physical guidance	high	High <i>(when needed)</i>	-
RM 1.11	Cognitive load of the human when operating the human-machine interface	low	High	Moderate
RM 1.12	Intuitiveness of the human-machine interface	high	High	Moderate
RM 2.1	Power transferred from the robot to the human in possible unintended collision <u>when the robot is static</u>	low	High	Moderate
RM 2.2	Magnitude of the force exerted to the human in possible unintended collision of the robot with the human <u>when the robot is static</u>	low	High	Moderate
RM 2.3	Power transferred from the robot to the human in possible unintended collision <u>when the robot moves (executes the task or actively observes the human)</u>	low	Should be variable	High
RM 2.4	Magnitude of the force exerted to the human in possible unintended collision of the robot with the human <u>when the robot moves (executes the task or actively observes the human)</u>	low	Should be variable	High
RM 2.5	Mean error between the learned trajectory and the motion of the robot (motion deviation) when executing the task	low	Moderate	Moderate

RM 2.6	Static compliance parameters of the robot when the human exerts forces to the robot intentionally	low	Should be variable	High
RM 2.7	Synchronization between the robotic arm and the platform	high	Low	Moderate
RM 3.1	Accuracy of the fruit shape detection	high	-	High
RM 3.2	Accuracy of the fruit orientation detection	high	-	Moderate
RM 3.3	Accuracy of the fruit position detection	high	-	High
RM 3.4	Accuracy of the human hand configuration detection	high	-	High
RM 3.5	Accuracy of the contact points detection	high	-	High
RM 4.1	Accuracy of occlusion detection	high	-	Moderate
RM 4.2	Effectiveness of the occlusion avoidance control scheme	high	-	High
RM 4.3	Accuracy of the human hand inference	high	-	Moderate
RM 4.4	Effectiveness of the “next best view” seeking algorithm	high	-	High
RM 5.1	Success rate of executions after the complete learning procedure for fruits of <u>similar</u> shapes and position/orientation (w.r.t to the robot platform) , as compared to the ones utilized for the learning	high	Very high	Very high
RM 5.2	Success rate of executions after the complete learning procedure for fruits of <u>different</u> shapes and position/orientation (w.r.t to the robot platform), as compared to the ones utilized for the learning	high	Very high	High
RM 5.3	Man-hour required to teach the skill for a new type of fruit	low	Very high	Moderate
RM 5.4	Similarity between the human motion and the one executed by the robot	high	Low	Moderate
RM 5.5	General success rate of the system after the training	high	Very high	High
RM 5.6	Average fruit picking cycle time after the training	low		Moderate
RM 5.7	Damage inflicted to the fruits from the robotic picking after the training	low		Very high

From the broader set of Related Measures (RMs), a refined selection has been identified as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to serve as critical benchmarks for evaluating the system's performance and impact. These KPIs are designed to measure the system's efficiency and effectiveness with precision. Table 3 outlines each KPI, its originating RM, the method of measurement, the indicative threshold value for success, and its definition, offering a comprehensive view of how performance will be assessed.

Table 3 – CARPOS KPIs

Key Performance Indexes	Related Measures	How it is measured	Indicative Value	How the indicative value is selected
KPI 1.1	RM 1.2 Number of iterations required for sufficiently capturing the human motion through vision	Number of iterations required to achieve satisfactory motion capture accuracy.	Max 5 iterations	Given the transient required to reach a new camera pose (point of view), this number is deemed as sufficient.
KPI 1.2	RM 1.9 Number of corrections done after the physical intervention of the human for corrections	Number of corrections required after human intervention.	Max 3 corrections	This number is deemed as the limit in order to induce low cognitive load to the user.
KPI 1.3	RM 1.7 Total cognitive load required for the teaching, reflected through the duration of teaching.	Time duration from the beginning of the teaching process, to the end of it	Maximum 4 hours	Cognitive load is proportional to the time duration required for a task, according to Fitts law ³
KPI 1.4	KPI 1.8 Total physical load required for the teaching, reflected by the total energy transferred from the human/user to the robot.	Energy as the integral of the power transmitted from the human to the robot, in each physical interaction	10 J in average <i>(during a single physical interaction)</i>	The Indicative value is selected based on the teaching of simple industrial task. ⁴
KPI2.1	RM 2.2 Magnitude of the force exerted to the human in possible	Magnitude of force	Max 100 N	The value is selected

³ Fitts, Paul M. (June 1954). "The information capacity of the human motor system in controlling the amplitude of movement". *Journal of Experimental Psychology*. 47 (6): 381–391. doi:10.1037/h0055392

⁴ D. Papageorgiou, T. Kastritsi, Z. Doulgeri and G. A. Rovithakis, "A Passive pHRI Controller for Assisting the User in Partially Known Tasks," in *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 802-815, June 2020, doi: 10.1109/TRO.2020.2969018.

	unintended collision of the robot with the human when the robot is static	exerted on the human during a potential collision when the robot is static.		such that no damage to the soft tissue of the human is occurred.
KPI2.2	RM 2.5 Mean error between the learned trajectory and the motion of the robot (motion deviation) when executing the task	Average deviation from the desired motion trajectory.	2 cm in position 5° in orientation	These values can serve as the limit for the trajectory tracking error in this specific task.
KPI3.1	RM 3.1 Accuracy of fruit shape detection	Percentage of correctly detected fruit shapes compared to the ground truth.	95%	A shape accuracy greater than this value will mean the insufficient grasp of the fruit.
KPI3.2	RM 3.3 Accuracy of fruit position detection	Accuracy of the detected position of fruits compared to their actual positions.	±2 centimeters	A position accuracy greater than this value will mean the insufficient grasp of the fruit.
KPI4.1	RM 4.1 Accuracy of occlusion detection	Percentage of correctly detected occlusions.	At least 90%	The inability of the occlusion detection method will heavily affect the active perception mechanism.
KPI5.1	RM 5.5 General success rate of the system after the training	Percentage of successful executions compared to the total number of attempts.	At least 90%	A 10 percent maximum error is tolerated.

KPI5.2	RM 5.7 Damage inflicted to the fruits from the robotic picking after the training	Percentage of fruits damaged after picking.	Maximum 5%	A 5 percent maximum damage is tolerated.
KPI5.3	RM 5.6 Average fruit picking cycle time after the training	Average time required to complete the picking of one fruit.	Average 30s	This is defined based on the human farmer activity.